

Large-scale multiactor training and mentorship programme to ASSist people with physical impairments in energy povERTy

D5.2 Report with the results of the open call

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ABOUT ASSERT

The ASSERT project primarily addresses the **nexus between energy poverty and disabled people**. The project aims to provide essential knowledge, competencies, and skills to key actors, such as policymakers, intermediaries, and directly affected persons, ensuring they can address energy poverty and mitigate its impacts.

Grounded on an understanding of the complex, intersecting challenges disabled people face, ASSERT approach emphasizes the importance of a targeted, inclusive response. The aim is to address three different target groups: **policy actors, intermediary/actors on the ground and people directly affected**.

During the implementation of the project, local policymakers and intermediaries have access to dedicated training and mentorship, with the aim to strengthen their knowledge and ability to efficiently tackle energy poverty for disabled collectives.

ASSERT, as part of the project methodology, has selected 25 pairs (formed by municipalities and intermediary organizations in Italy, Spain, France, Cyprus and Greece) which will undertake a **direct and customised mentorship** aiming at **filling their knowledge and capacity gaps**, with the objective to support them respectively in their activities on the ground and in the policy design. The jointly designed **training** will be made accessible to a wider audience to provide support to more local governments, aiming to share the knowledge gained to the widest possible audience. Each pair has the targeted mentorship outlined under a Programme Agreement, which is signed among the three parts: the municipality, the intermediary, and the respective responsible partner from ASSERT.

ASSERT consortium

No	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
1	AISFOR SRL	AISFOR SRL	IT
2	RETE ASSIST - ETS	RETE ASSIST - ETS	IT
3	ENERCOOP	ENERCOOP	FR
4	ASOCIACION ECOSERVEIS	ECOSERVEIS	ES
5	CITIZEN CROSSROADS	CCR	EL
6	ENERGEIAKO GRAFEIO KYPROU	CEA	CY
7	CLIMATE ALLIANCE - KLIMA-BÜNDNIS - ALIANZA DEL CLIMA e.V.	CLIMATE ALLIANCE	DE
8	EUROPEAN NETWORK ON INDEPENDENT LIVING BRUSSELS OFFICE	ENIL	BE
9	ETHNICON METSOVION POLYTECHNION	NTUA	EL
10	INSTITUTE FOR EUROPEAN ENERGY AND CLIMATE POLICY STICHTING	IEECP	NL
11	ACCADEMIA EUROPEA DI BOLZANO	Eurac	IT

Version History

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0.1	15/09/2025	Sofia Recio, Nona Galvany and Joan Estalella	Ecoserveis	First version of D5.2
0.2	25/09/2025	Quentin Géraud, Silvia Biancu, Myrto Skouroupathi and Konstantina Vougiouka	Enercoop, Rete Assist, CEA and CCR	
1.0	30/09/2025	Marina Varvesi and Virginia Dicuonzo	AISFOR	Submission to EC

Glossary

Acronym	Definition
DPO	Disabled People Organization
ToR	Terms of Reference

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Executive summary

The aim of this document is to explain the course of action for developing the ASSERT's call for mentorship, as foreseen under the framework of the project.

This report outlines the entire process of the mentorship call, including the design of the application survey, its dissemination, the steps undertaken to ensure the success of the call and the results for each country, specifying the pairs arranged and the proposed content for each mentorship.

The sections of this report describe the specific actions implemented during the Open Call process in each country, including the challenges encountered and the solutions enforced in order to achieve five pairs of municipalities and disabled people organizations (DPOs) in each pilot country, as this one the main goal of the call.

Furthermore, the report presents the different mentorship programme proposals developed by each pair, including the expected number of beneficiaries, the planned activities within the framework of ASSERT, and the outcomes of the mentorship. Every aspect is compiled in a programme agreement, specific to each pair, which is also addressed in the document.

The last point encompasses a "next steps" section for countries that have not reached five pairs yet, mentioning the actions that are being executed to achieve the goal of five pairs.

1. Mentorship structure and objectives¹

The ASSERT project works to develop pilot activities that are framed through a mentorship programme for municipalities and intermediary organizations.

The aim of the mentorship programme is to be implemented in the 5 countries of the project, which are Cyprus, France, Greece, Italy and Spain, having 5 pairs of municipality-intermediary per country. The selection of the 5 pairs is the outcome of the ASSERT Mentorship Call.

With the selected pairs, the experts' partners will provide **direct and customised mentorship** to **fill in the knowledge and capacity gaps** by supporting municipalities in their policy design activities, and intermediaries on the ground. The outcomes jointly designed for the 25 mentorship programmes, such as the target-specific **training** and the **policy and practical tools**, will be made fully accessible to provide support to a wider audience through local governments, therefore reaching and helping more citizens.

The mentorship is structured in a series of different steps, which include the following common actions:

- Identifying the knowledge gaps.
- Participating in the co-design of specific training material.
- Engaging other colleagues in the training process.
- Assessing the socio-political context through specific interviews with the final beneficiaries.
- Implementing targeted support actions with the intermediaries (customized per pilot country).
- Monitoring and evaluating the beneficiaries' condition after the implementation of the different actions.

The access to the mentorship was a transparent process through an Open Call, where interested organizations in each piloting country applied.

¹ This section about the mentorship structure and objectives is taken from the previous deliverable from the ASSERT project named D5.1. Terms of reference of Open Call including evaluation criteria.

2. Open Call for mentorship preparation²

The preparation of the Open Call was developed by the entire consortium and gathered in a previous deliverable called “Terms of reference of Open Call including evaluation criteria”. This process comprised several months of work, starting in October 2024, when the scene of the Open Call for the mentorship programme was set and municipalities were interviewed to assess gaps and training needs for policy actors. One month later, in November 2024, local pilots’ requirements were collected, and the call criteria was defined based on DPOs input. In January 2025, the final draft of the call was written with the aim to officially launch it in February 2025.

The documents compiled in the Terms of Reference (ToR) deliverable were drafted in English, and each national partner was responsible to adapt and translate them into the respective languages.

The documents were the following:

- **ASSERT MENTORSHIP ToR:** A document providing practical guidance to potential participants on how to submit a request to join the mentorship programme.
- **ASSERT APPLICATION FORM:** The form to be completed to apply for the mentorship call. It was available both online (to be filled out and submitted electronically) and offline (to assist applicants in preparing their submission).
- **FAQs:** A document answering frequently asked questions, made available to all applicants to ensure transparency.

The **ASSERT MENTORSHIP ToR** was divided into eight chapters, offering detailed information about the call and the project. The chapters are detailed below.

- **Chapter 1:** Provides an overview of ASSERT and the project's overall objective.
- **Chapter 2:** Introduces the connection between energy poverty and people with disabilities.
- **Chapter 3:** Describes the mentorship process and its components.
- **Chapter 4:** Focuses on the application form format, offering guidance on how to complete each section.
- **Chapter 5:** Provides additional information about the evaluation process.
- **Chapter 6:** Explains how the data in the proposals will be processed (GDPR).
- **Chapter 7:** Details how to submit additional questions.
- **Chapter 8:** Covers the agreement process for awarded proposals.

² This section includes content taken from the previous ASSERT project deliverable, D5.1. Terms of reference of Open Call including evaluation criteria.

The **ASSERT Application Form** was initially developed in Word to allow applicants complete it offline. The same structure was then uploaded online via the EU Survey platform. Each piloting country created a separate online application form in its national language to make the application process more accessible for evaluators and ensure that any questions from applicants were addressed by the appropriate responsible in each country.

The application form was divided into three sections:

1. **Organizations:** information about the applicants to better understand their background and experience.
2. **Partner Sections:** details on how the partners would collaborate and engage additional stakeholders and beneficiaries.
3. **Mentorship Request:** where applicants provided further details on their specific mentorship requests.

Additionally, the mentorship call package included a **FAQ** document. Originally drafted with anticipated questions, it was updated at the country level with new inquiries to ensure that all applicants received consistent responses.

2.1. EU Survey for the mentorship programme

The application for the mentorship programme was submitted through the [EU Survey](#).

The content of the EU Survey included:

- **Main contact information** for both the intermediary organization and the local government.
- **Name of other key stakeholders** that would be involved in the developing of the programme activities.
- **Information about the current actions** that are being developed to tackle energy poverty for vulnerable collectives, especially people with disabilities, including indicators, strategies and ongoing projects for this objective.
- **Information about the collaboration** between the intermediary organization and the local government, indicating if there are already joint actions or not.
- **A description of the mentorship** that both actors would like to receive, highlighting the capacity building needed, the final beneficiaries addressed, the impact foreseen, and the results of the mentorship programme for the beneficiaries.

Finally, the survey included a section that asked the local government and the intermediary organization to identify keywords that represented their needs when addressing the connection between energy poverty and people with disabilities. They were also asked to complete a self-evaluation from 1 to 5 (1 being minimum and 5 fully aware) about their understanding in tackling energy poverty. Also, another self-evaluation was given from 1 to 5 about their general support to people with disabilities.

2.2. Open call dissemination and promotion

Aiming to increase the number of submissions to the project's Open Call, dissemination and promotion actions were key to reaching the goal of five pairs per country. As mentioned before, the Open Call period started in February 2025 and was supposed to finish in June 2025, giving theoretically four months to find the 25 pairs of municipalities and disability support organizations (the latter also called DPOs or intermediaries). Details of this timeframe will be explained in the following sections.

To ensure the highest number of applications, dissemination and promotion actions were conducted.

2.2.1. Open call dissemination

On one hand, dissemination materials were developed and shared with all the project partners to become aligned with publications. Furthermore, ASSERT's LinkedIn page was used to foster general engagement by publishing call-related information as well as easy to republish content, so partners could easily republish the content that they wished.

On the other hand, each country used its own strategies and channels to disseminate the project's Open Call and to promote the informative webinars. These informative webinars were held during the months of January and February and appear detailed in the following section.

Week	Cyprus	France	Greece	Italy	Spain
1	03/02/25 - Email sent about the call opening	23 to 27/01/25 - Emails campaign	05/02/25 - LinkedIn post about the call opening and the upcoming webinar	3/02/25 - Emails sent about the call opening and the webinar link and invitation 14/02 - Informative webinar.	21/01/25 & 03/02/25 - Two posts on Social Media (each one on LinkedIn, FB, Instagram, X, Threads and Bluesky) about the call opening and the upcoming webinar https://shorturl.at/Rh40F
		04/02/25 LinkedIn post		From 3/02 - phone calls and several messages to municipalities and DPOs. Several LinkedIn posts published and news featured on RETE ASSIST newsletters.	From 03/02: Several emails sent to municipalities and DPOs
		05/02/25 Blog article			05/02/25 - 1st informative Webinar
2	11/02/25 meeting with Cyprus		13/02/2025 - invitation to municipality representative		10/02/25 - Social Media post published in LinkedIn, FB,

	Paraplegic organisation		s via email to attend the webinar		Instagram, X, Threads and Bluesky about the call opening and info about the 2nd webinar https://shorturl.at/iGu4n
				Emails and calls to the municipalities and DPOs.	From 07/02: Several emails sent to municipalities and DPOs
					12/02/25 - 2 nd informative Webinar From 12/02: Follow-up of the entities that participated in the webinars and others that we solved doubts via phone calls
3		19/02: Disability actors' platform publication (Idealco)	21/02/2025 - Contact via email more municipality representative s to inform them about the call - attach the webinar recording for		From 17/02: Follow-up of the entities that participated in the webinars

			more information		
5	03/03/25 meeting with SMILE centre 06/03/25 Meeting with the co-federation of people with disabilities	06/03/25 follow-up on e-mails campaign	04/03/2025 - Call the municipalities that were interested in the call and give them more information. Remind them the application procedure		
6	Newsletter with information about the call	11/03/25 LinkedIn post follow-up	10/03/2025 Check progress of municipalities - Inform them about the new deadline		11/03/25: Social Media post published in LinkedIn, FB, Instagram, X, Threads and Bluesky about the deadline extension of the call. https://shorturl.at/kL5OZ
7		17/03/25 follow-up on e-mails campaign	17/03/2025 - Check if any municipality applied through EU Survey	27/03 emails and calls to the municipalities and DPOs	21/03/25: Social Media post published in LinkedIn, FB, Instagram, X, Threads and Bluesky about the call and the meeting in Barcelona. https://x.com/Ecoserveis/status/1903037621485572335

				28/03 emails and calls to the municipalities and DPOs	
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2.2.2. Open call informative webinars

Each pilot country organized a minimum of one webinar to present the call and reply to the doubts raised from future participants. Each webinar was also recorded and made available online for other potential applicants.

To guarantee alignment in the messages, a basic set of slides were designed for each partner to be translated and modified to provide more information about energy poverty and the connection between energy poverty and physical disability.

The webinars for each country were held on different dates according to their needs and schedules.

Country	Date	Hour	Attendees	Comments
Cyprus	28/01/25 Webinar I (Greek)	10-11CET (11-12 local time)	8	Many attendees, especially from DPOs found it a useful programme to participate in. Three of the 8 participants ended up applying for the mentorship programme.
France	10/02/25 Webinar I (French)	11:00 - 12:00 (CET)	22 for 37 registered	Attendees really seem interested, several questions were asked. We offered to help in case one public actor is interested but can't find or convince the other part of the pair.
Greece	21/02/25 Webinar I (Greek)	10h00-11h00 (CET)	Municipality of Drama - Municipality of Naousa - Municipality of Veroia	Attendees seemed genuinely interested and asked a series of insightful questions. We offered to assist them if they struggle to find intermediaries interested in forming a pair. However, there were some concerns about the submission deadline, particularly regarding the time

				needed to find intermediaries and complete the application form
Italy	14/02/25 Webinar I (Italian)	10:00 - 11:00 (CET)	12 (4 municipalities and 4 organisations)	The attendees showed genuine interest and actively engaged by asking a number of insightful questions. Some participants also inquired whether any form of financial compensation was foreseen. We reassured them of our availability to provide support in case they encounter difficulties in identifying intermediaries willing to form a pair and in completing the application. At the same time, several concerns were raised regarding the tight submission deadline, particularly in relation to the time required both to secure intermediaries and to complete the application form.
Spain	05/02/25 Webinar I (Catalan)	12:00 - 13:00 (CET)	3 (1 DPO & 2 municipalities)	In both webinars, attendees were interested in the project and asked some questions about the assessment and the application process. Most of them agreed on the importance of connecting energy poverty and disabilities. We offered help to find municipalities or DPOs, as well as to write the proposal and complete the application through the EU Survey. Furthermore, we made
	12/02/25 Webinar II (Spanish)	12:00 - 13:00 (CET)	6 (2 DPOs & 4 municipalities)	

				ourselves available for individual meetings to resolve doubts.
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3. Mitigation actions

According to the ASSERT Grant Agreement, the open call process to select 25 pairs of municipalities and intermediaries as beneficiaries of the mentorship programme started in early February and was supposed to finish by the end of March.

To promote participation, emails were sent to municipalities to explain the project and encourage their involvement. These were followed by webinars and individual meetings with municipalities and intermediary organizations with the aim to assist them during the application process: writing the proposal, finding a municipality or intermediary to form a pair, and resolving doubts.

Despite all the efforts made by each pilot, recruiting suitable partners proved complex due to a range of structural and operational challenges across territories.

Key issues encountered include:

- Limited availability and resources in municipalities.
- Engagement issues with third-sector entities.
- Difficulty identifying qualified partners.
- Low awareness of the link between disability and energy poverty.
- Fragmented local coordination.
- Structural and logistical barriers.

By the end of March, few applications had been formalized across the five pilot countries. Since reaching potential participants was challenging due to the novelty of the proposal and the concerns encountered along the process, the call was extended in order to reach the 5 pairs objective per country. Therefore, the extension of the call could be considered the main mitigation action implemented across the five countries. Several extensions were granted: first until the end of April, afterwards until the end of June, and the last one until September.

There are countries where reaching an agreement was slow, especially because pilots had to wait for the answers of both the municipality and the DPO. At the same time, summertime did not help, thus hindering the communication and the possibility to formalize the call submission. This is why extending the deadline until September provided more margin to those pairs that were still applying for the call.

Each country applied targeted mitigation strategies according to their own context and pairs' situation. A detailed explanation is provided below:

Cyprus

In Cyprus, a few DPOs and municipalities had already shown interest before the deadline but could not complete the application in time. The two pairs of Nicosia-OPAK and Aradippou-KYSOA were fast to finalise their input with minor support from the local partner. The pair of Ayia Napa-SMILE (who is still pending submission at the time of writing) has prepared the applications but have requested a meeting with all participating members before submitting, to clarify some points about the mentorship plan. For the other two pairs, the mitigation action was contacting first the participants to the webinar of the call who showed interest in participating in the call. This easily led to the finding of the 4th pair of Athienou-SKE Athienou, after a meeting with the Mayor. Finally, Limassol was the other municipality which showed interest and we had identified through the interviews a potential DPO. Unfortunately, despite the desire of the staff to participate in the call, the DPO's Management Board rejected their request so we had to find another DPO. The municipality of Limassol then suggested another DPO that they already work together closer, with which we have been in contact and are waiting for the final approval to proceed with submission of the application. The biggest hurdle in securing the pairs was the hesitation from involved parties about the lack of capacity and benefits that they will have by joining.

France

In France, to disseminate the open call, Enercoop primarily relied on a national network of local authorities committed to fighting energy poverty at the local level (SLIME scheme). More than 75 local authorities were contacted, ranging from municipalities to inter-municipal structures and departments. Around fifteen local authorities expressed interest in the project, but several factors complicated their involvement. In a context of reduced public spending, with limited budgets and therefore limited human resources, it was difficult for staff to engage in innovation as proposed by the ASSERT project. Moreover, Enercoop faced strong pushback from local authorities regarding the idea of targeting a specific group of people. Within territorial schemes to combat energy poverty (such as SLIME), the French partner was questioned about the need to carry out specific actions for people with disabilities and was criticized for the perceived lack of inclusivity of these actions. Some local authorities justified their position by stating that their schemes already include all citizens and that there is no need for targeted aid for a specific group. It appears that adopting an intersectional approach is challenging for many stakeholders in the French context, where there is a strong desire to work with a unified and indivisible public, treating everyone equally without discrimination. However, this fails to take into account diversity, particularly that of people with

physical disabilities. Enercoop has encountered and continues to encounter significant difficulties in engaging intermediaries, most of whom have few or no employees, and even when they do, they do not have time for innovation. It is probably also because of this difficulty in finding motivated intermediaries that municipalities did not want to get involved in the experimentation.

Additionally, the project's initial focus solely on physical disabilities discouraged some disability organizations, which typically work across various types of disabilities. The target group was gradually broadened to include all types of disabilities, but since communications had already been widely disseminated, this adjustment had little impact on potential stakeholder engagement.

Faced with the difficulties of engaging municipalities, the French partner also reached out to national and local organizations in the disability sector. However, Enercoop encountered challenges due to its lack of visibility and limited knowledge of the actors in this field. Email campaigns were sent to Maisons Départementales des Personnes Handicapées (Departmental Houses for Disabled Persons), Centres Communaux et Intercommunaux d'Action Sociale (Municipal and Inter-municipal Social Action Centers), and Dispositifs d'Appui à la Coordination (Coordination Support Systems dealing with health issues), but very few of these actors responded.

Enercoop participated in strategy discussions organized by Ecoserveis to improve communication and stimulate engagement. It also held meetings with relevant national networks, both in the fight against energy poverty (Energy Cities, FLAME Federation - energy local agencies network, RAPPEL Network – Network of Actors against Poverty and Energy Poverty in Housing, Stop à l'Exclusion Énergétique - Stop Energy Exclusion) and in the field of supporting the autonomy of people with disabilities (Fédération des Aveugles de France - French Federation of the Blind, APF France Handicap, LADAPT, UNAPEI, APAJH and the National Group for the Inclusion of Physically Disabled Persons - support structures for several types of disability). Despite the presence of interested individuals who were convinced by the project's objectives, the same barriers mentioned earlier persisted.

It is also worth noting that signing agreements with municipalities involves delays because they must be approved by municipal councils. This process was even longer given that the project targeted large metropolitan areas, making administrative procedures more complex and time-consuming.

Greece

In Greece, the Municipality of Komotini, together with its DPO, expressed interest in participating after coming across the online material for the open call. They reached out, and the local partners informed them by email and phone about the project, its benefits, and the participation process. To identify additional candidates, the local partner first sent emails to municipalities to provide general information about the project. They also reconnected with the municipalities that had already been interviewed for another project task (Athens, Thermaikos, Veroia, Kifisia), in order to inform them about the mentorship opportunity, share further details, and encourage participation. When a response was received, the partner followed up directly with municipal staff, as the initial email might not have reached the right people. Afterwards, the local partner maintained regular communication with the municipalities to stay updated on the status of their applications, address any questions, and provide clarifications. They also shared updates regarding changes in deadlines and guided the municipalities on how to complete the required steps and respond to the application questions. In several cases, applications were delayed either due to slow communication, partly because of the holiday period, or because of internal municipal procedures and approval processes required before confirming participation in the initiative. In the case of Athens, a DPO was initially included in the first application. However, this DPO later withdrew, and since the Municipality of Athens wished to remain involved, it decided to participate through the Sustainable Mobility Department of the Municipality's Urban Planning and Environment Directorate.

Italy

In Italy, dedicated mitigation actions were implemented to successfully reach the five pairs, leading to a positive outcome despite the initial challenges. A key element of this process was the establishment of weekly calls, which ensured constant follow-up, nurtured trust, and helped build strong working relationships with the staff of the municipalities involved. These interactions were reinforced by regular email updates, communication via the Moodle platform, and dedicated newsletters, creating a continuous flow of information and sustained engagement.

To address the different levels of responsiveness, we designed a structured, step-by-step approach (Plan A, Plan B, Plan C, Plan D, and so forth), which allowed us to remain flexible and adapt to the feedback received from each municipality. The first municipalities we approached were Leverano, followed by Bari, Copertino, Milan, and Lecce. Each week, we carefully gathered feedback and refined our strategy accordingly.

Thanks to this iterative and adaptive process, we eventually succeeded in engaging the Municipality of Garaguso, a small town in southern Italy (Basilicata region), which formally agreed to join the mentorship programme. We expect the mentorship agreement to be signed by October.

Spain

In Spain, dedicated mitigation actions were adopted to reach the five pairs resulting in very successful outcomes.

First, it must be acknowledged that extending the deadline for completing the call was greatly appreciated by the applicants as, despite the proposal being attractive and very innovative, there were structural and logistical barriers that impeded the participation. Additionally, having designated team members from Ecoserveis available to address questions and provide support was highly beneficial, with some organizations even receiving assistance in drafting their applications. Another successful mitigation strategy was expanding the geographical scope of the call, which enabled a pair from Valencia to join the mentorship program.

During this process, we identified that the Municipality of Esplugues de Llobregat, besides showing strong interest in joining the programme, made the decision to participate very quickly. In contrast, in other municipalities it was often more challenging: meetings were usually held with technical staff who expressed interest but, due to time constraints or limited capacity, frequently did not take the final step. We also observed that Esplugues de Llobregat, together with other municipalities in Catalonia, had an action plan for people with disabilities, which facilitated engagement. This approach helped us to find another municipality with a local community and inclusion action plan, such as Igualada. Nevertheless, when contacting other municipalities with specific local disability action plans, some responded positively, but in most cases it was difficult to move the proposal forward.

In the city of Barcelona, we reached out at the beginning of the call Municipal Institute for People with Disabilities (IMPD), a key institution providing a wide range of inclusion and accessibility services for people with disabilities. Initially, IMPD indicated that they were not interested in joining the project. However, thanks to subsequent contacts through other municipal networks such as the Climate Shelters Network and ECOM, the Institute has since shown openness to discuss possible participation as a local stakeholder. As of early September, its involvement in the project is not yet confirmed, and efforts continue, with the support of other municipal actors, to encourage its eventual engagement.

4. ASSERT programme applications

The multi actor training and mentorship program, designed for pairs made of municipalities and organizations supporting people with disabilities, aims to establish connections between energy poverty and disability across the diverse contexts in five countries. Since the launch of the Open Call, each country has brought together various pairs eager to participate in the program. These pairs formalized their collaboration and involvement in the ASSERT project through a Programme Agreement, signed by three parties: the municipality, the DPOs, and the leading national partner of the project. This section provides a detailed overview of each pair participating in the ASSERT program, organized by country.

With respect to the evaluation process of programme applications, it should be acknowledged that no formal process was conducted by the ASSERT consortium, given the very low number of applications received. In fact, the process to gather five pairs per country was rather difficult and time-consuming. Although it was detailed in the ASSERT Grant Agreement that once the call was closed, two evaluators would assess each proposal for one month, picking five final pairs of municipalities and intermediaries in each piloting country, this process did not happen. The contract also foresaw a potential reserve list of participants in case of attrition of successful participants, but considering the situation that all countries encountered, direct awarding was executed without the need to arrange a reserve list. The way to formalize the participation of each pair to ASSERT’s mentorship programme was through the signature of a document that compiled all activities, timings, responsibilities and obligations of the mentorship, the so-called Programme Agreement.

4.1 CYPRUS

1st project pilot pair:

Municipality of Nicosia (submitted in May 2025)	
DPO: OPAK (Cyprus Paraplegic Organisation)	Local government: Municipality of Nicosia
Motivation: Investigating the possibility of forming an energy community for their members	Motivation: Part of their social policy
Requirements and barriers:	

The municipality has a good network of social workers but no understanding of the scale of energy poverty in the municipality.

OPAK has many members all over Cyprus who cannot install solar photovoltaics and are not aware of energy efficiency solutions.

No obstacles were faced during the recruitment phase.

Proposal description:

The municipality will receive help to map the problem of energy poverty and train the staff to respond to it. The plan is also for the municipality to put in place policies to tackle energy poverty.

OPAK would like to study the possibility of setting up an energy community for its members. Also, offer trainings for its members for available funding for energy efficiency upgrades.

Staff and beneficiaries:

The municipality's social work department and technical department will be involved.

OPAK has a team of carers that will be trained, as well as a management board that will be involved in the study for an energy community.

2nd project pilot pair:

Municipality of Aradippou (submitted in June 2025)	
<p>DPO:</p> <p>KYSOA (Cyprus Confederation of Organisations for Disabilities)</p>	<p>Local government:</p> <p>Municipality of Aradippou</p>
<p>Motivation:</p> <p>Cover the needs of member organisations</p>	<p>Motivation:</p> <p>Set up a monitoring plan</p>
<p>Requirements and barriers:</p> <p>The municipality has some energy poverty actions under its SECAP (Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan), which need to be implemented, but there is no expertise at the moment.</p> <p>KYSOA is looking to move into a new facility and some of its member organisations are also interested in upgrading their facilities.</p> <p>KYSOA has been reluctant due to capacity limitation, therefore many follow-ups were required to secure their participation.</p>	
<p>Proposal description:</p> <p>The municipal staff will be trained and a monitoring plan will be put in place.</p>	

Energy audits will be conducted by CEA (Cyprus Energy Agency) at the premises of KYSOA (and members) to suggest potential improvements.

Staff and beneficiaries:

The municipality has one neighbourhood social worker and other front desk officers, as well as technical staff who are responsible for monitoring the SECAP progress.

KYSOA has two staff members and each of its member organisations also have 1-2 staff members each.

3rd project pilot pair:

Municipality of Athienou (submitted in June 2025)	
DPO: SKE Athienou (Volunteers Council of Athienou)	Local government: Municipality of Athienou
Motivation: Build a stronger and more educated volunteer base	Motivation: Build a stronger and more educated volunteer base
Requirements and barriers: The Municipality and DPO work very closely for the past 40-50 years. Expertise on working with people with disabilities is high but there is no awareness about the issue of energy poverty. No obstacles were faced during the recruitment phase, however this is a smaller municipality, which might cause issues in meeting the target numbers.	
Proposal description: Series of trainings to volunteers and staff to build capacity in order to help people with disabilities and also respond in emergency cases (e.g. heatwaves).	
Staff and beneficiaries: 2-3 staff members from the municipality and a large number of volunteers from the DPO.	

4th project pilot pair:

Municipality of Ayia Napa (submitted in September 2025)	
DPO: SMILE Project - Autism Support Famagusta	Local government: Municipality of Ayia Napa
Motivation:	Motivation:

Improve conditions in permanent living facilities.	Coordinate with DPO for future facilities.
<p>Requirements and barriers:</p> <p>The Municipality has been working with the DPO to receive funding for upgrading the permanent living facilities for people with disabilities. The DPO has direct needs for improving the conditions until a larger upgrade can be achieved.</p> <p>The application is ready but they have not submitted yet, since they have requested a trilateral meeting prior to submission. There is communication to secure a date.</p>	
<p>Proposal description:</p> <p>Study the current facilities and future plans to improve living conditions for the people with disabilities</p>	
<p>Staff and beneficiaries:</p> <p>Both technical staff and social workers of the municipality are involved. The DPO has two carers and a larger number of volunteers.</p>	

5th project pilot pair:

Municipality of Limassol (pending)	
<p>DPO:</p> <p>Pancyprian Association for the Rehabilitation of the Disabled (POAA) Limassol</p>	<p>Local government:</p> <p>Municipality of Limassol</p>
<p>Motivation:</p> <p>Strengthen the collaboration with the municipality of Limassol</p>	<p>Motivation:</p> <p>Adhere to Mission 100 requirements and train social workers.</p>
<p>Requirements and barriers:</p> <p>The Municipality is a Mission 100 city and has to implement and monitor actions on energy poverty.</p> <p>A DPO had confirmed their interest to participate, however after passing the decision through the Management Board, they have rejected the proposal to participate, quoting capacity limitations. A new DPO was found and is in the process of completing the application for the call.</p>	
<p>Proposal description:</p> <p>Identify indicators for energy poverty and a monitoring plan for the municipality. Strengthen the network of social workers of the municipality that are helping the members of POAA.</p>	

Staff and beneficiaries:

The municipality has 7 social workers who will be involved in the process together with the staff and board of the DPO. The beneficiaries of the specific DPO are people with various physical disabilities who are either eligible for governmental support or not.

4.2 FRANCE

1st project pilot pair:

Municipality of Besançon (submitted in March 2025)	
<p>DPO:</p> <p>APF France Handicap (Association of Paralysed People of France) Bourgogne Franche-Comté</p>	<p>Local government:</p> <p>City of Besançon (Energy Management Division)</p>
<p>Motivation:</p> <p>The association has adopted a strategic plan for the 2024-2028 period, titled Straight Ahead, Rights for the Future, which envisions a more just, inclusive and sustainable society, rooted in human rights. It provides daily support to 200 beneficiaries in a medico-social center in the area of Besançon, parallely working on access and retention to housing.</p>	<p>Motivation:</p> <p>The City Council of Besançon has been leading an ambitious initiative to tackle energy poverty since 2013 (SLIME), providing free technical and social assistance at the households' homes, in collaboration with external partners. They pay particular attention to targeting groups most at risk of energy poverty, such as the elderly, students, and single mothers. People with disabilities have been identified as among the most vulnerable, making it essential for them to implement a strategy to better identify at-risk situations and offer personalised solutions to support individuals with disabilities.</p>
<p>Requirements and barriers:</p> <p>The pair needs external support to enhance the collaboration between both structures in a relevant and long-term purpose.</p> <p>They have identified the dependence of people with disabilities on energy and the damage caused by its absence. However, they are not able to act preventively or provide support that meets our challenges.</p>	
<p>Proposal description:</p> <p>The pair wants to create a peer group so that disabled people can actively participate in the energy transition and fight for the right to energy. They also wish to make home visits</p>	

to inform the concerned households about energy efficiency measures and support them as best as possible to help them address their situation of energy poverty.

Staff and beneficiaries:

APF France Handicap Bourgogne Franche-Comté could engage the director of the delegation, one person of the staff and a lead volunteer, as well as the social staff composed of 5 people (social assistants).

The city council of Besançon could engage the energy poverty coordinator, the internal specialised educator responsible for individual household support and the development of collective actions with vulnerable households. They could also possibly engage sporadically two people from the staff – a thermician and a facilitator.

Another stakeholder, the social action city centre could engage the accessibility and Disability Expert referent supporting the territorial coordination of the project.

2nd project pilot pair:

Municipality of Paris (submitted in October 2025)	
<p>DPO:</p> <p>City of Paris (Solidarity Department) - to be confirmed</p>	<p>Local government:</p> <p>City of Paris (Ecological Transition and Climate Division Department)</p>
<p>Motivation:</p> <p>The Solidarity Department, through the Disability Service of the Autonomy Sub-Directorate, works to support people with disabilities by funding social institutions.</p>	<p>Motivation:</p> <p>The local authority is keen to experiment with the ASSERT team as part of their local scheme to combat energy poverty, which brings together various social players in the area (SLIME,. In addition, last year the city launched a Parisian observatory on energy poverty, which is exploring the impact of energy poverty on health. The city has already identified specific problems for the elderly and people with disabilities, and is currently looking at ways of improving user pathways and identifying local intermediaries. The ASSERT project represents an opportunity to better address disability-related issues.</p>
<p>Requirements and barriers:</p> <p>Our referent at the City of Paris and the ASSERT team put out feelers to the representative of people with disabilities on the Departmental Council for Citizenship and Autonomy and the Departmental House for People with Disabilities, as well as to DPOs such as the</p>	

regional delegation of APF France Handicap. All refused. Leads to other DPOs are currently being evaluated.

Many departments within the City of Paris referred us to another department when the ASSERT team contacted them. There are many departments, and as the issue affects several of them, it seems very complicated for a single department to agree to work on the project.

Proposal description:

The City of Paris wishes to carry out support initiatives that are directly adapted to the energy needs of people with disabilities. The solidarity department is interested in obtaining objective data on how disability impacts energy situations.

It also wants to work more closely with local actors in the disability field, both public and private, to identify households in difficulty.

The Parisian Departmental Houses for Disabled Persons could give feedback on the experiment periodically. A social housing actor has also agreed to take part in the project, but as an additional stakeholder not specialising in disability.

Staff and beneficiaries:

Another stakeholder, a social housing actor, could engage 2 project managers.

3rd project pilot pair:

Lille European Metropolis (submitted in September 2025)	
<p>DPO:</p> <p>Inhari</p>	<p>Local government:</p> <p>Lille European Metropolis (Private Housing Department)</p>
<p>Motivation:</p> <p>Inhari is an inter-regional association that supports individuals and local authorities in their housing renovation projects. The association's activities include adapted housing.</p> <p>Inhari is part of the public local scheme to combat energy poverty. This operator, in the frame of this local scheme provides support to disabled households.</p>	<p>Motivation:</p> <p>The local authority is keen to experiment with the ASSERT team as part of their local scheme to combat energy poverty, which brings together various social players in the area (SLIME).</p> <p>As part of this programme, the private housing department has launched a scheme to combat substandard housing, adapt homes and renovate energy-efficient buildings. The metropolis is committed to the Facile À Lire et à Comprendre (easy to read and understand) approach. It has created a guide for tenants adapted to their comprehension</p>

	<p>difficulties and plans to introduce Facile À Lire et à Comprendre on its website in 2025.</p> <p>Partnerships are also being developed with the city's hospitals to carry out accessibility work on homes following their operations.</p>
<p>Requirements and barriers:</p> <p>The metropolis and the social housing actor are not familiar with the energy needs of the target audience.</p>	
<p>Proposal description:</p> <p>The pair wish to strengthen their capacity to combat energy poverty by renovating homes for people with disabilities.</p> <p>One possible action could also be to work with the Maison de l'Habitat Durable (sustainable housing centre), jointly managed by the metropolis and the city of Lille. It has a programme of events (40 to 60 free events per quarter), including modules on energy poverty.</p>	
<p>Staff and beneficiaries:</p> <p>Two people from the private housing department should be involved in the project. On the social housing actor side, 1 or 2 people working on the adapted housing aspect of their activity should also be involved in the project.</p>	

4th project pilot pair:

Greater Lyon Metropolis (submitted in September 2025)	
<p>DPO:</p> <p>APF France Handicap (Association of Paralysed People of France) Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes</p>	<p>Local government:</p> <p>Greater Lyon Metropolis (Safety, Health and Environment Department)</p>
<p>Motivation:</p> <p>The Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes regional delegation of APF France Handicap, through its medical-social establishment, which provides daily support to 200 beneficiaries in the city of Lyon, and through its advocacy work in defence of the rights of people with disabilities, has agreed to work with the Lyon Metropolis within the framework of their local scheme to combat energy poverty,</p>	<p>Motivation:</p> <p>The local authority is keen to experiment with the ASSERT team as part of their local scheme to combat energy poverty, which brings together various social players in the area (SLIME).</p> <p>The Safety, Health and Environment Department has approved the project.</p>
<p>Requirements and barriers:</p>	

The city does not have any information about households with disabilities or their specific energy needs.

For its part, the regional delegation has very little knowledge of the issues that people with disabilities may encounter in relation to energy.

Proposal description:

The pair wants to take effective and appropriate action to combat energy poverty among people with disabilities by providing solutions in terms of energy efficiency and renewable energy through tailored support during home visits to households (in addition to better identify them). There are also plans to set up a peer group so that people with disabilities can actively participate in the energy transition, thanks to contacts made by the regional delegation of APF France Handicap.

A social housing actor involved in the SLIME mechanism, has also agreed to take part in the project, but as an additional stakeholder not specialising in disability.

Afm Téléthon (French association against muscular dystrophy) has expressed an interest in working sporadically on the project.

The Gabriel-François Richard Foundation is inclined to organise activities in five of its independent living facilities for around fifty people with disabilities.

Staff and beneficiaries:

At least one person from the Safety, Health and Environment Department could work with the ASSERT team and at least one person from APF France Handicap Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes could work with the ASSERT team.

4.3 GREECE

1st project pilot pair:

Municipality of Komotini (submitted in March 2025)	
<p>DPO:</p> <p>Perpato Association</p>	<p>Local government:</p> <p>Municipality of Komotini</p>
<p>Motivation:</p> <p>The DPO is motivated to ensure that the specific needs and rights of persons with disabilities are fully integrated into local energy policies and actions. Participation in the ASSERT programme will help them strengthen their advocacy role, build knowledge on energy poverty, and</p>	<p>Motivation:</p> <p>The Municipality of Komotini seeks to improve its understanding and response mechanisms to energy poverty, especially for vulnerable groups such as persons with disabilities. The Municipality is motivated to enhance its capacity, institutional coordination, and data collection</p>

<p>empower their members to engage meaningfully in energy-related decision-making processes. The DPO also aims to influence the design of more inclusive, accessible, and equitable energy solutions at the municipal level.</p>	<p>procedures to implement more targeted and effective interventions.</p>
<p>Requirements and barriers:</p> <p>The Municipality of Komotini does not have a specific policy on energy poverty or dedicated procedures addressing the energy needs of persons with disabilities. There are no institutionalized indicators linking disability and energy poverty, making needs identification difficult.</p> <p>Needs are assessed mainly through KEPA data, social research, and individual reports. However, variations in energy needs depending on the type and degree of disability are not systematically addressed.</p> <p>There is no energy office or specialized staff within the Municipality. Cross-referencing data with other institutions (for example OPEKA) faces legal and administrative obstacles. Due to limited financial and human resources, interventions focus mainly on basic social support.</p> <p>In the context of the ASSERT project, coordination with the Municipality of Komotini has so far proceeded smoothly, with no significant obstacles in communication or collaboration. However, challenges have arisen on the side of the participating NGO. As the organization operates on a voluntary basis, its representatives are not consistently available, which has occasionally hindered timely responses and effective engagement.</p>	
<p>Proposal description:</p> <p>Through the mentorship, the Municipality aims to better understand energy poverty and begin taking meaningful action to raise awareness and support the everyday lives of its residents. In collaboration with Social Services and local NGOs, they wish to co-host outreach events and disseminate information through the NGOs' established networks, ensuring broader reach.</p>	
<p>Staff and beneficiaries:</p> <p>Four municipal staff and four intermediary operators from the Perpato Association are planned to be trained, with the programme aiming to support approximately 70 households.</p>	

2nd project pilot pair:

<p>Municipality of Veroia – regional unit of Imathia (submitted in April 2025)</p>	
<p>DPO:</p> <p>Ta paidia tis anoixis NGO</p>	<p>Local government:</p> <p>Municipality of Veroia</p>

<p>Motivation:</p> <p>The organization "Ta Paidia tis Anoixis" supports people with disabilities by promoting autonomy and social inclusion. Addressing energy poverty is a key concern, especially for households with disabled members. Participation in the program aligns with its mission, strengthening its ability to offer practical, daily-life training and improve living conditions through targeted energy support.</p>	<p>Motivation:</p> <p>The municipality is motivated to join the program as, despite offering a wide range of social services, there are no targeted policies or monitoring tools addressing energy poverty specifically for people with physical disabilities. Participation in the program would fill this gap, enabling more inclusive support and better living conditions for this vulnerable group.</p>
<p>Requirements and barriers:</p> <p>The municipality requires external support to build internal capacity for addressing energy poverty in a way that is inclusive of people with disabilities. Key needs include staff training, development of targeted policies, and tools to monitor and assess energy vulnerability in this population. However, the municipality faces several barriers, such as the lack of disaggregated data, limited experience in disability-specific interventions, and the general nature of existing welfare programs, which are not tailored to the specific challenges faced by people with disabilities in managing energy needs.</p> <p>As an organization supporting people with disabilities in developing autonomy and life skills, "Ta Paidia tis Anoixis" requires technical guidance, staff training, and access to funding in order to integrate energy poverty mitigation into its programs. The organization is well-positioned to support this population but faces barriers including limited financial resources, reliance on external partners, and the absence of structured methodologies for addressing energy needs within the context of disability support and daily living training.</p> <p>Additional barriers were encountered in engaging the municipality with the ASSERT project. While the municipality expressed interest early on, particularly following the initial announcement of the mentorship programme, challenges emerged prior to the final submission of applications. Due to a heavy workload and limited time availability, municipal staff were hesitant to commit to the project's activities. Furthermore, inconsistent communication proved to be a recurring obstacle. Email correspondence was often ineffective, with direct phone calls serving as a more reliable method of reaching municipal staff and progressing collaboration.</p>	
<p>Proposal description:</p> <p>The municipality of Veroia aims to identify key indicators and establish monitoring mechanisms to better assist people in need. As part of this effort, they plan to use online platforms and social media channels to share accessible information and registration links, while also providing virtual info sessions and remote assistance via phone or video calls to ensure inclusive and timely support.</p>	

Staff and beneficiaries:

Four municipal staff and three intermediary operators from the Community Center are planned to be trained, with the programme aiming to support approximately 70 households.

3rd project pilot pair:

Municipality of Thermaikos (submitted in March 2025)	
<p>DPO:</p> <p>Youth Council</p>	<p>Local government:</p> <p>Municipality of Thermaikos</p>
<p>Motivation:</p> <p>The Youth Council of Thermaikos is motivated to join the mentorship programme because they want to create a local youth agenda that supports their community. They work to connect young people with the local government and help young voices be heard in municipal decisions. Although they don't have executive power, they advise the municipality and promote new projects that benefit the community, like helping people with disabilities who face energy poverty.</p>	<p>Motivation:</p> <p>The Municipality of Thermaikos is motivated to better address energy poverty at the local level, especially for vulnerable groups such as persons with disabilities. Participating in the ASSERT programme offers them the opportunity to develop targeted actions, receive expert mentorship, and access tools to integrate inclusive energy strategies into local policies. Additionally, the Municipality is driven by the prospect of leveraging European funding to strengthen local energy communities and deliver long-term social and environmental benefits.</p>
<p>Requirements and barriers:</p> <p>Under current law, local municipalities have limited authority to intervene. Social tariffs are administered by the state rather than the municipalities. Municipal social services primarily offer information and assist vulnerable individuals with their applications, guiding them towards the appropriate programs. Support for extra energy costs for people with disabilities is only available through national programs. Local governments have not been granted these responsibilities, though some municipalities advocate for change via the Central Union of Municipalities in Greece and other initiatives. There is no cooperation with social services or private actors to address disabled persons' energy needs. In Thermaikos, social services underperform, and no separate disability allowance is provided by the municipality. The municipality exempts people with disabilities from municipal cleaning, water fees. However, it does not yet provide emergency aid for energy needs.</p> <p>Furthermore, barriers to municipal engagement in the ASSERT project became evident following the initial announcement of the mentorship programme. CCR made many efforts to engage the municipality through multiple formal invitations and outreach</p>	

efforts. However, a number of barriers hindered effective collaboration. A key challenge has been the slow-paced internal communication processes within the municipal system, which significantly delayed responses and made real-time coordination difficult.

Proposal description:

In collaboration with the Youth Council, the Municipality of Thessaloniki implements numerous volunteer initiatives. To enhance their impact, youth volunteers need targeted training to understand and effectively communicate the concepts of energy poverty, enabling them to take informed and meaningful action within their communities.

Staff and beneficiaries:

The programme plans to train 3 municipal staff members and 5 intermediary operators from the Youth Council, supporting approximately 60 households.

4th project pilot pair:

Municipality of Athens (submitted in May 2025)	
<p>DPO:</p> <p>Sustainable Mobility Department of the Municipality's Urban Planning and Environment Directorate</p>	<p>Local government:</p> <p>Municipality of Athens</p>
<p>Motivation:</p> <p>The Department wants to train its staff through ASSERT so they can better manage issues related to energy poverty and disability, develop awareness and sensitivity, build capacity, and ensure there is trained personnel to lead future initiatives for a sustainable, inclusive, and accessible city.</p>	<p>Motivation:</p> <p>The Municipality of Athens is motivated to participate in the mentorship programme to address the currently unmet needs of people with disabilities facing energy poverty. Through this programme, the municipality aims to develop targeted policies and improve its understanding of the intersection between disability and energy poverty, ultimately enhancing support services for vulnerable residents.</p>
<p>Requirements and barriers:</p> <p>Although the municipality has explicitly recognized disability as a category eligible for exemptions, no implementation mechanisms have been activated yet and there are still no targeted policies addressing the intersection of disability and energy poverty. The energy issue on people with disabilities has not been a topic of discussion yet, and the nexus of disability and energy poverty has not been addressed or recognised. At the same time, the department acting as intermediary along with the municipality are well aware of the difficulties faced by these citizens and with great care, recognise efforts (especially those that feel they have tangible results) and wish to make a life better for everyone. But still, accessibility in the city is a very particular concern, as many still face</p>	

obstacles in navigating streets and sidewalks due to inadequate, blocked or non-existing ramps.

Proposal description:

The municipality of Athens plans to reinforce the already established energy poverty alleviation office to provide services for people with disabilities. This department is already up and running, serving as a central point for providing in-person information, guidance, and tailored support to vulnerable households, with specialized staff such as social workers helping individuals access resources and navigate procedures. To effectively implement this step, the staff will require additional training in order to better understand the concept of energy poverty and disability and provide more comprehensive and informed support. In regards to the Department involved, the training will support future actions implemented through the Municipality as matters such as accessibility and inclusion are high on their agenda.

Staff and beneficiaries:

Three municipal staff members and four trained intermediaries will participate in the programme, assisting around 100 households.

5th project pilot pair:

Municipality of Kifisia - Athens metropolitan area (submitted in June 2025)	
<p>DPO:</p> <p>Community Center</p>	<p>Local government:</p> <p>Municipality of Kifisia</p>
<p>Motivation:</p> <p>The Community Center is highly motivated to engage in the mentorship programme to support vulnerable groups, particularly people with disabilities, in overcoming energy poverty. They work closely with vulnerable groups which allows them to raise awareness about energy poverty and help individuals access available resources and support. Their role is essential in connecting the disabled community with the services and information they need.</p>	<p>Motivation:</p> <p>The Municipality of Kifisia has actively participated in previous initiatives related to the energy transition, demonstrating its commitment to sustainable development. However, there are currently no similar initiatives specifically supporting people with disabilities facing energy poverty within the municipality.</p> <p>This mentorship programme represents a valuable opportunity, and Kifisia is very interested in engaging with it to fill this gap. The municipality is motivated to contribute to and support the initiative, aiming to ensure that vulnerable groups receive the necessary assistance to improve their energy access and affordability.</p>

Requirements and barriers:

There are currently no specific actions targeting vulnerable groups in the energy sector, nor partnerships or service exchanges to support them. No indicators or funding exist specifically for the energy needs of persons with disabilities.

The municipality primarily focuses on upgrading municipal buildings and improving conditions for employees and students, while also advancing projects like controlled parking and energy efficiency upgrades. At the same time, it recognizes the significant accessibility barriers faced by persons with disabilities, including limited mobility in urban areas, inaccessible public buildings, and a lack of inclusive infrastructure such as playgrounds. Although more specialized interventions, particularly those addressing issues like energy poverty among people with disabilities, are high on the municipality's agenda, they have yet to be prioritized in practice.

Additionally, engaging the municipality with the ASSERT project revealed several operational challenges. Initial communication was difficult, as responsibility for managing the mentorship programme application was transferred between multiple employees. This lack of continuity created confusion and made it hard to establish effective coordination with the individual in charge of submission. Furthermore, the municipality faced difficulties identifying staff members willing and able to participate in the training activities and commit to the ASSERT programme. The heavy workload during standard working hours left little room for extra responsibilities, such as training sessions. Although the relevant department eventually created time slots to allow staff members to engage with ASSERT, the internal procedures required to make these arrangements were complicated and time-consuming, resulting in further delays.

Proposal description:

Municipality of Kifisia plans to reactivate its energy community, focusing on vulnerable groups, especially people with disabilities. To do this successfully, they need a strong foundation with well-trained staff who can provide the right support and help set clear goals. They are also interested in learning more about funding opportunities, as they have already been involved in some EU projects.

Staff and beneficiaries:

Three municipal staff and three intermediary operators from the Community Center are planned to be trained, with the programme aiming to support approximately 80 households.

4.4 ITALY

1st project pilot pair:

Municipality of Parma (submitted in May 2025)

<p>DPO:</p> <p>National Association of Families of People with Intellectual and/or Relational Disabilities - (ANFASS) - Parma</p>	<p>Local government:</p> <p>Municipality of Parma</p>
<p>Motivation:</p> <p>ANFFAS seeks to acquire tools and knowledge to support families facing energy poverty, particularly those with members with intellectual and developmental disabilities. The association aims to improve communication and awareness within its network and empower individuals to make informed decisions about energy use and rights, including access to protected energy markets.</p>	<p>Motivation:</p> <p>The city has identified a lack of structured data and experience in addressing energy poverty among people with disabilities. Through this pilot, the municipality aims to build competencies, explore best practices, and develop inclusive policies and communication tools to support this vulnerable group effectively.</p>
<p>Requirements and barriers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of existing data and structured experiences linking disability and energy poverty • Need for inclusive communication tools • Necessity for increased awareness among both municipal staff and beneficiaries • Challenges in reaching diverse disability communities • Limited access to or awareness of rights (e.g. returning to regulated energy market) 	
<p>Proposal description:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide joint training to both municipal staff and NGO workers on the intersection of disability and energy poverty • Develop effective, respectful communication methods and tools tailored to people with disabilities • Launch awareness campaigns during regular community events • Establish pathways for people with disabilities to re-enter the protected energy market • Capitalize on partnerships with associations like Polisportiva Gioco and the Anmic Parma (National Agency for the Protection and Representation of Persons with Disabilities) to reach a broader audience and ensure inclusivity across disability types 	

<p>Staff and beneficiaries:</p> <p>Staff involved:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● National Association of Families of People with Intellectual and/or Relational Disabilities - ANFFAS: 2 operators ● Polisportiva Gioco: 2 operators ● ANMIC Parma (National Body for the Protection and Representation of Persons with Disabilities): 2 operators ● Comune di Parma: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2 from the Department of Ecological Transition ○ 2 from the Adult Disability Service ○ 2 from the Territorial Agency for Energy and Sustainability <p>Beneficiaries:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Direct: 100 people with disabilities involved in empowerment paths ● Indirect: Up to 300 families reached through community events and outreach ● Broader network includes 40 active ANFFAS families and 500 supported families, 200 Polisportiva Gioco members, and 3,000 Anmic Parma (National Agency for the Protection and Representation of Persons with Disabilities) members

2nd project pilot pair:

Municipality of Arezzo (submitted in March 2025)	
<p>DPO:</p> <p>Foundation Arezzo Comunità</p>	<p>Local govern:</p> <p>Municipality of Arezzo</p>
<p>Motivation:</p> <p>The Foundation aims to strengthen its ability to support families with disabilities facing energy poverty. It seeks to acquire technical and methodological tools to develop impactful local solutions, focusing on inclusivity, autonomy, and sustainable energy practices.</p>	<p>Motivation:</p> <p>The municipality is committed to reducing energy poverty among its most vulnerable citizens, especially people with disabilities. It needs external mentorship to improve its integration of social and disability-related aspects into energy policy and service provision, as well as to build replicable, inclusive solutions through training and pilot interventions.</p>
<p>Requirements and barriers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Limited internal expertise on energy poverty specific to disabled populations 	

- Need to develop replicable models for energy and social inclusion
- Demand for tailored tools and training for operators and stakeholders
- Gaps in household-level data and customized solutions
- Need to coordinate among social services, energy services, and community stakeholders

Proposal description:

The ASSERT mentorship will be used to:

- Train municipal and foundation staff on energy poverty as it relates to disability
- Conduct energy diagnostics and propose improvements in 15 households
- Inform and engage families with physical disabilities on energy efficiency
- Create a replicable strategic action plan for disability-inclusive energy interventions
- Support a campaign to promote access to energy bonuses and behavioral change
- Ensure wide stakeholder engagement and prepare a final project model document

Staff and beneficiaries:

Staff involved:

- **Municipality of Arezzo:** 5 staff members from Ufficio Servizi Sociali
- **Foundation Arezzo Comunità:** 3 staff members + 6 operators from disability associations and third-sector service providers

Beneficiaries:

- **Direct:** 50 families with physical disabilities (based on income, severity, housing)
- **Wider outreach:** At least 30 people attending the stakeholder information event
- **Additional reach:** Energy audits for 15 households

3rd project pilot pair:

Municipality of Serrenti (submitted in April 2025)	
<p>DPO: Caritas Serrenti</p>	<p>Local government: Municipality of Serrenti</p>
<p>Motivation: Caritas Serrenti wishes to deepen its understanding of energy poverty and disability to more effectively support</p>	<p>Motivation: Facing depopulation and demographic aging, Serrenti aims to pilot inclusive energy transition models that combine</p>

<p>beneficiaries through targeted actions. The goal is to strengthen their role in fostering dignity and inclusion for individuals facing social and economic hardship, many of whom live in energy poverty and/or with disabilities.</p>	<p>technical innovation and social care. The municipality seeks mentorship to build strategic capacity, especially around the intersection of disability and energy vulnerability, and to develop replicable tools and training for operators and citizens.</p>
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- Requirements and barriers:**
- Lack of training among municipal and social staff on energy poverty for people with disabilities
 - Limited public awareness and tools for inclusive energy education
 - Need for coordination with local stakeholders for wider impact
 - A small community with dispersed resources and services
 - Disconnection between energy planning and real needs of vulnerable families

- Proposal description:**
- The mentorship will support:
- Training for municipal staff, Caritas volunteers, and local service providers
 - Awareness campaigns and inclusive materials to reach and engage vulnerable families
 - Pilot interventions addressing home energy needs for 70 individuals with disabilities
 - Collaborative meetings and human-centered design workshops for citizens with disabilities
 - Development of a strategic model to influence regional policy and future municipal action
 - Synergy building with academic, environmental, and media partners

- Staff and beneficiaries:**
- Staff involved:**
- Comune di Serrenti: 5 staff and stakeholders (technical and social service)
 - Caritas Parrocchiale: volunteers and coordinators (5–10 expected to be directly trained)
- Beneficiaries:**
- Direct: Over 70 individuals with physical and cognitive disabilities
Wider outreach: Families in social/economic hardship supported by Caritas monthly

- Community engagement: Through shared events, consultations, and training activities

4th project pilot pair:

Municipality of Roma I (submitted in July 2025)	
<p>DPO: CER Le Vele</p>	<p>Local government: Municipio Roma I</p>
<p>Motivation: CER Le Vele seeks to expand the reach of its pioneering energy-solidarity model by scaling inclusive solutions to tackle energy poverty among people with disabilities. The mentorship will help improve its capacity in social impact analysis, project scaling, and beneficiary outreach.</p>	<p>Motivation: The municipality needs support in navigating the unique energy challenges of a historic, urban, and demographically complex area. It seeks tools and strategies to integrate social vulnerability and disability into local energy efficiency and climate action policies.</p>
<p>Requirements and barriers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complexity of energy upgrades in historical buildings • High number of single, elderly residents living in suboptimal housing • Limited tailored frameworks connecting disability with energy transition • Need for systematic mapping of vulnerable families • Scarce cross-sector operational models for inclusive energy support 	
<p>Proposal description: The mentorship will aim to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build operational tools to map energy poverty among people with disabilities • Provide training for local government and CER operators on inclusion and efficient energy practices • Develop a research-action project linking energy vulnerability with disability • Improve outreach and communication strategies on energy rights and CERs • Foster social inclusion and empowerment through community participation • Support replication of CER Le Vele's solidarity-energy model in other urban settings 	
<p>Staff and beneficiaries: Staff involved:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipio I Roma: 5 Municipal staff from social services and climate action 	

- CER Le Vele: 5 Technical-scientific staff, including from Scenario B and local associations

Beneficiaries:

100 people with disabilities between:

- Residents of the Leonarda Vaccari Institute (people with disabilities)
- Families in vulnerable economic conditions from the local neighborhood
- Broader community members benefitting from information points and training

4.5 SPAIN

1st project pilot pair:

Barcelona City (submitted in April 2025)	
<p>DPO:</p> <p>Sindicat de Mares en la Diversitat Funcional (Union of Mothers in Functional Diversity)</p>	<p>Local government:</p> <p>Punts d'Assessorament Energètic, called PAE (Energy Advice Points of Barcelona City Council, Social Rights Area)</p>
<p>Motivation:</p> <p>Raise awareness of the needs of families with minors with functional diversity by creating a support network among mothers. They want to increase the knowledge of energy poverty, energy and water bills.</p>	<p>Motivation:</p> <p>Collaboration with the aim of detecting and improving procedures in the PAE service, as well as making the Union aware of the public service to facilitate referral and improve support.</p>
<p>Requirements and barriers:</p> <p>The City Council's main objective is to ensure that all citizens have access to basic services, regardless of their economic circumstances. The City Council also aims to support vulnerable people in the city by strengthening the community fabric.</p> <p>The Union has identified the need for social workers at disability care centres to have a better understanding of the assistance and subsidies available to people with disabilities in different areas, such as care and the purchase of specific devices and materials.</p>	
<p>Proposal description:</p> <p>Preparation and adaptation of two informative workshops that will last between one hour and one hour and a half for several members of the Union who do not reside in Barcelona.</p> <p>On the one hand, a first workshop will be held to explain the main concepts of the electricity bill, introduce the social electric bonus, and guide participants on how to apply</p>	

for it. A second workshop will focus on understanding the water bill and presenting the measures available to protect vulnerable consumers.

On the other hand, a dedicated support service will be implemented for all families who are members of the Union and reside in Barcelona. This service will assist them in applying for the social electric bonus and in extending disability benefits, as well as in accessing support from the Catalan Water Agency. The aim is to ensure that all eligible families can successfully apply for these social benefits.

Finally, awareness will be raised on the PAE service as a reference for dealing with situations of energy poverty, guaranteeing protection and access to basic supplies in situations of vulnerability.

Staff and beneficiaries:

Staff involved:

- Barcelona City Council: 2 technicians.
- Union of Mothers in Functional Diversity: 5 people will take part.

Beneficiaries:

- Direct: 30 households with criteria to get social bonus in energy bill
- Indirect: All the members of these families and other members of the union

2nd project pilot pair:

Municipality of Igualada (submitted in April 2025)	
<p>DPO:</p> <p>Fundació Privada Àuria (Àuria Private Foundation)</p>	<p>Local government:</p> <p>Department d'Acció Social (Social Action Department of Igualada City Council)</p>
<p>Motivation:</p> <p>Improve support for disabled people that experience energy poverty, while building the capacity of the professionals who assist them.</p>	<p>Motivation:</p> <p>Learn about how to mitigate energy poverty for disabled people by training professionals and providing useful knowledge to the affected collective.</p>
<p>Requirements and barriers:</p> <p>In this sense, the local government needs protocols and specific training to identify and prioritise households with people with disabilities who are in energy vulnerability.</p> <p>At the same time, Àuria Foundation requires practical training on utility bills, energy-saving measures, processing benefit applications, and adapting communication to serve diverse needs.</p>	

Finally, the beneficiaries need accessible tools and personalised support to understand, manage and improve their energy situation, as well as their rights.

Proposal description:

The objective of the mentorship program is to conduct 3 workshops, each lasting 1.5 hours, on energy use at home, aimed at people with disabilities and the educators/workers who support them. These workshops will be focused on three key topics: learning about easy-to-read utility bills, energy efficiency and the social bonus.

Also, one support point to assist in the application process for the social bonus will be offered. A specific day and time slot will be set to offer this service to those interested.

A guide document will be prepared for professionals with updated information on the available aid and benefits for people with disabilities who are in a situation of energy vulnerability.

Finally, an easy-to-read leaflet will be provided with basic energy-saving tips.

Staff and beneficiaries:

Staff involved:

- Igualada City Council: 1 educational housing support technician.
- Àuria Private Foundation: 1 social educator.

Both professionals will contribute 6 hours per week, in total.

Beneficiaries:

- Direct: 50 people with disabilities who have been users of one of the local public services.
- Indirect: All the members of these families.

3rd project pilot pair:

Municipality of Esplugues de Llobregat (submitted in April 2025)	
DPO: Esplugues Sense Barreres (Esplugues Without Barriers)	Local government: Servei d'Atenció a la Diversitat i Esplugues Energia (Disability Care Service and Energy Esplugues of Esplugues City Council)
Motivation: Esplugues Without Barriers joins the project with the aim of eliminating physical, social and administrative barriers that affect people with reduced mobility and sensory	Motivation: Esplugues City Council is engaged in addressing energy poverty through the Esplugues Energy service and the <i>Pla d'Atenció Integral a les Persones amb Discapacitat i Diversitat Funcional</i> (in

<p>disability. As a local organisation with deep knowledge on the needs of people with disabilities, the entity is committed to promoting accessibility and social inclusion through energy education and adapted support services.</p>	<p>English: Comprehensive Care Plan for Persons with Disabilities) from 2023 to 2027. With a cross-sectoral and participatory approach, the municipality seeks to ensure that energy resources and services are accessible and equitable for all, especially for people in vulnerable situations.</p>
<p>Requirements and barriers:</p> <p>Key challenges include the lack of accessible information formats, the complexity of electricity bills, and limited participation of people with disabilities in energy-related decision-making. Additionally, public services and local initiatives must be better coordinated and adapted to meet the real needs of this group.</p>	
<p>Proposal description:</p> <p>The project involves joint action by Esplugues City Council (Disability Care Service and Energy Esplugues) and Esplugues Without Barriers to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop an Accessible Energy Use Best Practices Guide, ensuring everyone can understand and apply efficient consumption advice. • Host inclusive information sessions using adapted materials to promote participation of persons with disabilities. • Workshops to understand electricity bills to improve clarity and enable everyone to understand basic concepts of energy consumption. <p>Workshops with the aim to offer tools to ensure an optimal and efficient use of the energy at home.</p>	
<p>Staff and beneficiaries:</p> <p>Staff involved:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Esplugues City Council: 2 technicians • Esplugues Without Barriers: 2 staff members <p>Beneficiaries:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct: 180 users with disabilities in energy poverty situations. • Indirect: All the family members from the household. And among 4,000 residents with legally recognised disabilities, those who are facing an energy poverty situation. 	

4th project pilot pair:

Municipality of València (submitted in July 2025)

<p>DPO:</p> <p>Associació de Fibrosis Quística Comunitat Valenciana (Cystic Fibrosis Association of the Valencian Community)</p>	<p>Local government:</p> <p>Fundació València Clima i Energia (Valencia Foundation Climate and Energy)</p>
<p>Motivation:</p> <p>Cystic Fibrosis Association of the Valencian Community requests support from ASSERT to co-design and implement a tailored energy advisory service for families affected by cystic fibrosis. These households face specific challenges: continuous use of medical devices, the need for stable indoor temperatures, and extended time at home, all resulting in high energy needs and costs.</p>	<p>Motivation:</p> <p>The Foundation would like to adapt some communication material and gain knowledge through workshops about energy poverty and the available subsidies to disabled people.</p>
<p>Requirements and barriers:</p> <p>The Valencia Foundation Climate and Energy assists people in situations of energy poverty, but their protocols are designed for vulnerable individuals without specific attention to people with disabilities. Therefore, it is important to identify and understand the special needs of this group to ensure quality support and provide adapted materials that facilitate comprehension and practical application.</p> <p>The knowledge gained will be disseminated to other entities that want to raise awareness on energy efficiency and energy poverty with the aim to support families in need. The beneficiaries need accessible tools and personalised support to understand, manage and improve their energy situation, as well as their rights.</p>	
<p>Proposal description:</p> <p>The proposed action includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Online training sessions to understand the concepts included in an energy bill, information about social electric bonus and energy efficiency at home. ● Online training sessions (to reduce infection risks) for the Cystic Fibrosis Association. ● Personalised energy advice (bills, social bonus, energy efficiency) ● Development of accessible educational materials ● Training of Cystic Fibrosis Association staff. ● A stable referral protocol to the municipal Energy Offices <p>This initiative builds on Valencia Foundation Climate and Energy existing energy advisory service and strategic work on energy vulnerability, and Cystic Fibrosis Association’s long-standing support of around 40 families annually living with cystic fibrosis.</p>	

The collaboration will be extended to 3 other entities:

- Municipal department: Oficina Municipal d'Atenció a la Diversitat (Municipal Office for Diversity Support), related to giving support to people with functional diversity, which they are interested in receiving a workshop regarding energy poverty addressed to this collective.
- A federation of DPOs that work with people with functional diversity: Plena Inclusió Comunitat Valenciana (Full Inclusion Valencian Community). They are interested in adapting easy-to-read materials to facilitate the understanding of energy saving and efficiency concepts for people with intellectual disabilities. Workshops aimed at families with high dependence on technology at home due to health issues would also be valued.
- There's another entity that is interested in organising workshops oriented to families with people with functional diversity. This entity is Associació Valenciana d'Ajuda a la Paràlisi Cerebral (Valencian Association for Cerebral Palsy Support), which is an association for cerebral palsy assistance.

Staff and beneficiaries:

Staff involved:

- Valencia Foundation Climate and Energy: 1 energy technician from FVCE + 1 staff from Energy Office. However, the training material will be forwarded to more municipality staff.
- Cystic Fibrosis Association: 1 person from staff and 1 association's social worker and psychologist.

The training material for DPOs will be forwarded to more persons within the Cystic Fibrosis Association.

Beneficiaries:

- Direct: 30–40 families with one or more members with cystic fibrosis in the Valencia region who are facing economic vulnerability and, probably, energy poverty due to their dependency on electrical medical equipment.
- Indirect: Staff and families beneficiaries from this agreement, since the Municipal Office for Diversity Support, Full Inclusion Valencian Community and Valencian Association for Cerebral Palsy Support may be part of the programme too.

5th project pilot pair:

Municipality of Barcelona (not submitted yet)	
<p>DPO:</p> <p>ECOM (acronym referring to organizations collaborating with people with disabilities)</p>	<p>Local government:</p> <p>Xarxa de Refugis Climàtics Barcelona (Network for Climate Shelters Barcelona) and Institut Municipal de Persones amb</p>

	Discapacitat, called IMPD (Municipal Institute for People with Disabilities)
<p>Motivation: Promoting the knowledge of people with disabilities to empower them in accessing energy, as well as supporting the social workers who provide them with assistance in their daily tasks.</p>	<p>Motivation: Considering the needs and requirements of persons with disabilities in all actions and communication strategies, ensuring full accessibility.</p>
<p>Requirements and barriers: The current communication materials and messages are aimed at the general population of Barcelona and do not consider the specific needs of people with disabilities. Therefore, training is needed to identify these needs and to understand what language adaptations are required to ensure accessibility. People with disabilities need to learn strategies and daily habits to improve their comfort and to be better prepared for unexpected energy-related issues.</p>	
<p>Proposal description: As part of the Barcelona City Council's Heat Plan, various communication actions and materials are developed during the summer to inform people about what they can do during a heat wave and where to find the nearest climate shelters to cope with extreme temperatures. In all these actions, it is important to include the perspective and needs of people with disabilities, aiming to adapt materials, messages, and advice to their conditions in order to ensure their inclusion within the City Council's Plan. ECOM users and personal assistants will participate on tailored trainings covering the following topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Climate resilience and strategies to cope with heat ● Understanding bills and existing benefits such as the social bonus ● Concepts of home comfort, energy-saving measures, and strategies to address "blackouts" affecting essential equipment <p>Finally, a pool of advisory hours to resolve questions after the training, will be available for end users and personal assistants.</p>	
<p>Staff and beneficiaries:</p> <p>Staff involved:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Barcelona City Council: 1 technician ● ECOM: 35 staff members <p>Beneficiaries:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Direct: All the users of people who are users of Personal Assistance Service ● Indirect: All the family members from the household. 	

6th project pilot pair:

Municipality city of Terrassa (still to be defined)	
<p>DPO:</p> <p>Oficina de Capacitats Diverses i Accessibilitat (Diverse Abilities and Accessibility Office of Terrassa City Council)</p>	<p>Local government:</p> <p>Oficina Municipal d'Atenció a la Pobresa Energètica i la Promoció d'Eficiència Energètica, called OFIMAPE (Municipal Office for Energy Poverty Assistance and Energy Efficiency Promotion of Terrassa City Council)</p>
<p>Motivation:</p> <p>Promote the inclusion and rights of people with disabilities in energy transition, ensuring their active participation in decisions that affect them and avoiding a welfare-based approach</p>	<p>Motivation:</p> <p>Adapt the energy advice office brochures to make them accessible and understandable for people with disabilities, ensuring their comprehension of energy rights and energy efficiency.</p>
<p>Requirements and barriers:</p> <p>The Municipal Office for Energy Poverty Assistance assists people in situations of energy poverty, but their protocols are designed for vulnerable individuals without specific attention to people with disabilities. Therefore, it is important to identify and understand the special needs of this group to ensure quality support and provide adapted materials that facilitate comprehension and practical application.</p>	
<p>Proposal description:</p> <p>With the aim of improving the local response capacity to energy poverty in households with people with disabilities, the proposal focuses on three key areas:</p> <p>Collaboration with other municipalities in the co-design of training sessions to ensure that all materials and content are accessible to different municipal technicians.</p> <p>Adaptation of existing leaflets and brochures into easy-to-read format to ensure maximum inclusivity for people with disabilities.</p> <p>Training to address the knowledge gaps on energy poverty identified within the group of people with disabilities.</p>	
<p>Staff and beneficiaries:</p> <p>Staff involved:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Terrassa City Council - Diverse Abilities and Accessibility Office: 2 staff members from entities that collaborate with the Office for People with Disabilities. • Terrassa City Council - OFIMAPE: 2 municipal energy technicians. 	

Beneficiaries:

- Direct: 150 users with disabilities.
- Indirect: Family members from the users' households. Nevertheless, the Terrassa City Council can reach 18,500 residents of Terrassa who are disabled. .

5. Programme Agreement

The programme agreement is the document that serves to establish a formal written agreement between the three parties: the national entity representing the ASSERT project, the municipalities, and the intermediary organizations. This document outlines all the conditions, responsibilities, and commitments of the involved parties in the project. The purpose of the programme agreement is to ensure that all parties clearly understand their obligations and the terms of collaboration, providing a legal foundation for the implementation of the project.

The programme agreement includes details about the project's objectives, activities to be carried out, expected outcomes, project duration, as well as aspects such as data protection and confidentiality. Additionally, it is a crucial tool to ensure that all parties comply with the agreed-upon conditions and to provide a clear and shared understanding of each party's responsibilities within the project framework.

At the time of writing this report, although most of the candidatures have confirmed their participation in the mentorship, not all programme agreements have been signed. The involvement of the municipalities' legal departments caused delays in the process, leading to some cases where the signing was postponed for several months due to legal reviews and modifications to the agreements.

The structure of the programme agreement is the same for all 25 pairs. Each country contributed with suggestions and inputs regarding content and structure to produce a comprehensive and commonly used commitment document across the different pilot initiatives. Each country has translated the original document for its respective pilot, adapting the relevant sections according to the specific proposals of each pair, as well as adjusting confidentiality and data protection aspects to comply with national regulations.

The programme agreement is an exhaustive document that gathers all mentorship details through 9 sections, which are the following:

- Objective and scope, considering the general objective of the ASSERT project, the objective and description of the ASSERT programme, the geographical scope of the pilot, the dedicated target group and beneficiaries in each case.
- Expected results and impact, in which every country adapted the content according to the agreed mentorship for each pair, mentioning specificities and targeted assistance.
- Contribution to ASSERT, including a dedicated table summarizing each activity, timing and format for both the DPO and the municipality.

- Rules and responsibilities of the parties, to make clear what was expected from the mentorship programme for all parties.
- Procedures in case of force majeure or significant deviations.
- Confidentiality and data protection, including personal data protection and GDPR regulations, as well as obligations of the parties.
- Duration and termination, indicating how long the programme agreement would last according to the general duration of the project.
- Communication, visibility and language, including communication tools and the working language of the agreement, which differed in each country.
- Finally, the last point included the signatures of the three parties: the municipality, the DPO or intermediary organization, and the leading national partner.

A complete model document of the programme agreement is included in annex number 2.

The following tables summarise the status of each agreement by pair and country:

Cyprus		
Municipality	DPO	Programme Agreement
Nicosia	OPAK	Pending - October 2025
Athienou	SKE Athienou	Pending - October 2025
Aradippou	KYSOA	Pending - October 2025
Ayia Napa	Smile	Pending - October 2025
Limassol	POAA Limassol	Pending - October 2025

France		
Municipality	DPO	Programme Agreement
City of Besançon (Energy Management Division)	APF France Handicap (Association of Paralysed People of France) Bourgogne Franche-Comté	Pending - End of September 2025
City of Paris (Ecological Transition and Climate Division Department)	City of Paris (Solidarity Department) - to be confirmed	Pending - November 2025
Lille European Metropolis (Private Housing Department)	Inhari	Pending - November 2025

Greater Lyon Metropolis (Safety, Health and Environment Department)	APF France Handicap (Association of Paralysed People of France) Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes	Pending - December 2025
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Greece		
Municipality	DPO	Programme Agreement
Komotini	Perpato NGO	Signed
Veroia	Ta paidia tis anoixis NGO	Pending of signature / Expected by the end of October
Thermaikos	Youth Council	Signed on behalf of the DPO / expected by the end of October
Athens	Department of Sustainable Mobility of the Directorate of Urban Planning and Environment of the City of Athens	Pending of signature / Expected by October 20
Kifisia	Community Center	Signed

Italy		
Municipality	DPO	Programme Agreement
Municipality of Parma	National Association of Families of People with Intellectual and/or Relational Disabilities - (ANFASS) - Parma	Sent 10/06/2025 – Pending signature but revisions done by the DPO and the administrative office of the municipality. Expected to be signed by October
Municipality of Arezzo	Foundation Arezzo Solidale	Signed in August 2025
Municipality of Serrenti	Caritas Serrenti	Signed in August 2025
Municipality I of Rome	CER Le Vele	Sent September/2025 – Pending signature but revisions done by the DPO and the administrative office of the municipality.

		Expected to be signed by October
Municipality of Garaguso	To be confirmed	The application and the Program agreement hasn't been completed nor signed yet. All the information and signatures will be available at the beginning of October.

Spain		
Municipality	DPO	Programme Agreement
Punts d'Assessorament Energètics de l'Ajuntament de Barcelona (Àrea de Drets Socials)	Sindicat de Mares en la Diversitat Funcional	Sent 02/06/2025 – Pending of signature but already ongoing as all parts agreed to start the programme without the formality of the signature not to delay activities. Expected to be signed by October
Municipality of Igualada (Departament d'Acció Social)	Fundació Privada Àuria	Signed in July 2025
Municipality of Esplugues (Esplugues Energia and Pla d'Atenció Integral a les Persones amb Discapacitat i Diversitat Funcional)	Esplugues Sense Barreres	Revision done by the legal department of the City council. Pending of signature. Expected to be signed by October
Xarxa Refugis Climàtics (Climate Shelters Network) and Institut Municipal de Persones amb Discapacitat from Municipality of Barcelona	ECOM	Still defining the final proposal. There have been certain obstacles. Unknown date of signature, but expected in October.
Municipality of València - Fundació València Clima i Energia	Associació de Fibrosis Quística Comunidad Valenciana	Pending of signature. Expected to be signed by October
Municipality of Terrassa - OFIMAPE (Energy Advisory Centre)	Municipality of Terrassa – Capacitats Diverses	Still to define the final proposal. It has been a

		complex negotiation. Unknown date of signature.
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6. Next steps

This section is dedicated to those countries who did not manage to reach five pairs of municipalities and DPOs. These countries have the opportunity to explain in this section how they will proceed to reach the necessary pairs, mentioning the current situation and future actions. At the same time, this section serves to highlight, in a general approach, how many programme agreements are waiting to be signed in each country.

Cyprus

Five pairs have been identified, yet we are finalising the programme agreement to personalise the support to each beneficiary, after consultation with each one of them. None have signed the Programme Agreement but are expected to do so within October.

France

Four pairs have been identified, and the four programme agreement signatures are still pending. Three of these pairs are awaiting approval from the municipal or metropolitan office, and with regard to the city of Paris, research is still ongoing to determine which city services will be the intermediary and local service.

As mentioned earlier in this report, numerous municipalities and intermediaries were contacted in France. Advanced discussions took place with some local authorities, but these cities ultimately declined due to a lack of human resources and knowledge of local disability stakeholders (Carcassonne, Dijon Métropole, Marseille). Contact details for these cities were kept on file in case of any withdrawals during the trial year.

Enercoop focused on peers with a municipality that was genuinely interested in participating in the experimentation, namely the cities of Besançon and Paris and the metropolitan areas of Lyon and Lille. As three of these municipalities are among the largest in France and given the lack of significant interest from other local authorities, the KPIs were revised from five to four peers, increasing those of the largest cities.

Close contact is still ongoing with these four local authorities so that the programme agreements can be signed as soon as possible. It has been clarified with these municipalities that ASSERT support will begin as soon as possible, even

if the programme agreement has not yet been signed. This is particularly the case for the city of Lille, which will not be able to sign its agreement until the end of the year.

As mentioned above, municipalities have also encountered obstacles in engaging intermediaries to build their partnerships. Currently, Enercoop and the city of Paris are facing the same situation, where it is very difficult to find an intermediary. A hybrid solution for collaboration between the city and the intermediary is being created through an agreement outside the ASSERT project on a local scheme to combat energy poverty. This would enable the city of Paris to commit to the project by signing the agreement without an official intermediary, while working on the ASSERT topic with local disability stakeholders with whom they will collaborate as part of their partnership agreement on combating energy poverty.

Greece

In Greece, five pairs of municipality and intermediary organizations have been established. Programme Agreements are expected to be signed from both sides by the end of October, with two fully signed agreements and the remaining pending.

Italy

For the fifth pair, the Municipality of Garaguso has informally agreed to sign the mentorship agreement. At the current stage, however, no Disabled People's Organization (DPO) has yet been identified, and the candidature module has not been completed. For this reason, we cannot provide many further details at the moment.

Nevertheless, we are maintaining weekly discussions with the municipal administration to support them in the process of identifying a suitable DPO partner and in completing all the relevant information required for the application. This close and continuous engagement is intended to ensure that the municipality is fully supported and that the mentorship can proceed smoothly once all elements are in place.

On the other hand we are just waiting for the mentorship agreement formal signature from the Municipality of Rome I and the Municipality of Parma, but they agreed to do it by the end of September.

Spain

In Spain, six proposals were confirmed. However, at the time of writing this deliverable, the Terrassa proposal has been put on hold due to political changes in the local government, but no formal withdrawal from the project has been communicated.

So far, one programme agreement has been signed, and four more are expected to be signed in October. For the sixth pair, the timing is uncertain due to the difficulties encountered, as explained before.

A strategy has been activated to contact other potential participants and to establish a reserve list, should new complexities arise for the approved pairs.

7. Annexes

Annex 1: Programme Agreement template

Large-scale multiactor training and mentorship programme to ASSist people with physical impairments in energy povERTy

ASSERT Programme Agreement

Training and mentoring programme

Disclaimer: Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

This PROGRAMME AGREEMENT is made on XX/XX/2025, within the framework of the service CONTRACT N° 101167584 — LIFE23-CET-ASSERT named: “ASSERT” signed on 24/06/2024 (hereinafter referred to as the “PRINCIPAL AGREEMENT”), between:

XXXX, as local authority
represented by xxx

xxx, as Intermediary organisation
established xxx
represented by xxx

xxx as ASSERT Consortium member
established xxx
represented by xxx

collectively called the ‘Parties’, represented by their authorised representatives.

The Parties have agreed as follows:

OBJECTIVE AND SCOPE

I. General objective of the ASSERT project

The general objective of the ASSERT project, cofounded by LIFE programme, is to address the lack of adequate knowledge and skills among key actors involved in tackling energy poverty, with a specific focus on people with disabilities. ASSERT aims to empower local policymakers, frontline workers, intermediaries, and persons with disabilities through an integrated, multi-actor training and mentorship programme. The project targets the three key recommendations on skills from the 2023 EU energy poverty guidelines:

1. training for policymakers and energy professionals on energy poverty and the clean energy transition,
2. training of frontline social and health workers to identify and support energy-poor households, and
3. targeted education for energy-poor individuals — including those with low digital literacy — to help them better manage their energy needs and engage in the just energy transition. By adopting a participatory, bottom-up approach based on gap and SWOT analyses, ASSERT seeks to break the vicious cycle linking disability, poor housing conditions, and worsening health by enabling access to efficient, affordable, and renewable energy solutions.

II. Objective and description of the ASSERT programme

The general objective of the technical assistance is to support the implementation of the ASSERT pilot by providing expertise, coordination and direct support to ensure effective inclusion of persons with disabilities who are affected by energy poverty. This assistance will focus on facilitating access to adapted training and mentorship activities, improving the capacity of local actors to address the specific needs of this target group, and supporting their active participation in the design and uptake of energy efficiency and renewable energy solutions.

Specifically, the technical assistance aims to:

Each pilot should introduce 2-3 objectives of their technical assistance to the pair Municipality – Intermediary organization.

This technical assistance contributes to the overarching objectives of ASSERT by ensuring that the project methodology is effectively applied and locally adapted, with a strong focus on inclusion, accessibility, and empowerment.

The delivery of technical assistance in this programme will be based on the following methodology:

Each pilot should describe how will be their technical assistance to the pair Municipality – Intermediary Organization, taking into account the identified needs and the agreed approach during the previous meetings.

The mentorship programme starts with the signing of this Programme Agreement. The intermediary will then be called to participate in a focus group to help identify the knowledge gaps. Then, the intermediary will be called to offer feedback and/or input in the structure and content of the training for intermediaries. Simultaneously, the local authority will participate in the needs assessment to help co-design the training for local authorities. As a next step, the two trainings will be offered by the ASSERT Consortium member to the local authority and the intermediary. They will then complete the ex-ante questionnaire to enable the support by both the local partner and the European partners. The local authority and intermediary will in turn offer support to the main target group, in order to directly tackle energy poverty. Once the support is offered, some ex-post questionnaires will be filled in by both the intermediary and the local authority, so that the ASSERT consortium partner can assess the effectiveness of the Mentorship Programme.

III. Geographical scope of the pilot

The geographical scope by the activities above defined is the Municipality of XXXXXXXXX in XXXXXXXX. The technical assistance under this agreement specifically supports the Catalan municipality of XXXXXX and the Disabled People Organization (DPO) of XXXXXXXXX and focuses on ensuring the effective involvement of persons with disabilities affected by energy poverty in the design, delivery, and evaluation of ASSERT activities.

In Catalonia (Spain), the provider of this training and mentorship programme is led by the organisation Ecoserveis, which will act as the local coordinator.

IV. Target group and beneficiaries

The mentorship programme within ASSERT in municipality of XXXXXXXXX is designed to engage and support the following target groups and direct beneficiaries:

Primary target groups

To adapt by each pilot in each Programme Agreement...

- **Local public administrations and municipalities**, particularly departments responsible for social services, energy, housing, or inclusion policies. These actors play a key role in designing and implementing measures to address energy poverty at local level.
- **Intermediary Organization / Disabled Persons' Organisations (DPOs)** and other civil society organisations working with and for people with disabilities. These organisations act as intermediaries, advocates, and service providers, with a deep understanding of the challenges faced by their constituencies.

Final beneficiaries

To adapt by each pilot in each Programme Agreement...

- **People with disabilities** living in or at risk of energy poverty. This group is particularly vulnerable due to a combination of low income, high energy needs (e.g. due to assistive devices, heating or cooling needs), and structural barriers to accessing energy-related support and information.

Additional stakeholders indirectly involved

If proceed, to adapt by each pilot in each Programme Agreement...

- **Frontline workers**, such as social workers, community health professionals, or energy advisors, who support vulnerable households and can help identify needs, provide guidance, and channel resources.
- **Family members**, who often play a central role in managing household energy use and advocating for people with disabilities.
- **Energy actors** (e.g. local energy agencies, utilities or cooperatives), who may contribute technical expertise or support the implementation of inclusive solutions.

The programme adopts a multi-level and participatory approach, recognising the interconnected roles of institutions, organisations and individuals in effectively addressing energy poverty among persons with disabilities.

EXPECTED RESULTS AND IMPACT

The mentorship programme aims to build capacity among **municipality of XXXXXXXX** and Disabled Persons' Organisations (DPOs) **XXXXXXXXXX** to better understand, address and integrate the specific needs of people with physical disabilities affected by energy poverty. By fostering mutual learning and collaboration, the programme is expected to generate the following results and impact:

Expected results

To adapt by each pilot in each Programme Agreement...

- **Increased awareness** among local authorities and DPOs about the intersection between energy poverty and disability.
- **Improved institutional capacity** to identify and reach energy-poor persons with disabilities, through tailored tools, strategies and support mechanisms.
- **Co-design of local actions** and policies that are inclusive, data-informed, and responsive to the realities of people with physical disabilities.
- **Development of long-term cooperation frameworks** between municipalities and DPOs, promoting joint ownership of solutions.
- **Enhanced confidence and knowledge** among DPO staff and municipal officers on how to support inclusive energy transitions.

Expected impact

To adapt by each pilot in each Programme Agreement...

- **Reduction of structural barriers** that limit access to energy efficiency and renewable energy solutions for people with disabilities.
- **Increased uptake of inclusive energy poverty measures** in local plans and services.
- **Empowerment of persons with disabilities** to participate actively in the energy transition and advocate for their rights.

This mentoring programme in the Municipality of **XXXXXXX** is expected to assist **20** households (add agreed KPIs).

CONTRIBUTION TO ASSERT

Apart from receiving the Technical Assistance, the municipality of **XXXXXX** and DPO **XXXXXXX** will participate in the following activities as part of the programme.

	Task / Activity	Description	Estimated Time	Format
INTERMEDIARY ORGANIZATION / DISABLED PEOPLE ORGANIZATION	Focus groups with intermediaries	Participation in 2 focus groups to identify needs and experiences.	2 x 2h sessions	Online or in-person
	Co-creation of training content	Feedback and input on course structure and materials via working sessions.	~3h (across meetings)	Online meetings
	Participation in online course	Completion of an online training	~Minimum 3 h self-paced	Online (asynchronous)
	Ex ante and ex post evaluation	Impact assessment of materials and informal trainings for disabled people in fighting energy poverty	~Minimum 15 ex ante survey ~Minimum 5 ex post survey	Online or in person (survey)
LOCAL AUTHORITY	Needs assessment	Completion of a survey or attendance at an online meeting to identify gaps.	~2 x 3 h	Online (survey/meeting)
	Co-creation of training content	Feedback and input on course structure and materials via working sessions.	~3h (across meetings)	Online meetings
	Training sessions (online & in-person)	Participation in training sessions adapted to local needs and context.	~5 x 2h total	Online + face-to-face

Gantt Chart and actions provided by CEA to be adapted by every pilot (original chart in the [folder](#)):

Mentorship Programme																		
Activity	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18
	may-25	jun-25	jul-25	ago-25	sep-25	oct-25	nov-25	dic-25	ene-26	feb-26	mar-26	abr-26	may-26	jun-26	jul-26	ago-26	sep-26	oct-26
1. Sign Programme agreement	█																	
2. Participate in a focus group to identify knowledge gaps (intermediaries)		█	█	█														
3. Participate in the co-design of trainings (local authorities & intermediaries)		█	█	█														
4. Complete training for intermediaries				█	█	█	█	█										
5. Complete training for local authorities				█	█	█	█	█										
6. Ex-ante questionnaires			█	█	█													
7. Support by the local partner and other EU partners through: - direct contact point for energy efficiency and RES-related questions - regular meetings for updates and queries - technical expertise for the DPO's facilities (if decided) - policy analysis and co-creation with local authority (if decided) - any additional tasks agreed					█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
8. Direct assistance to target					█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
9. Ex-post questionnaires																█	█	█

RULES AND RESPONSIBILITIES OF THE PARTIES

It is agreed that **ASSOCIACIÓ ECOSERVEIS** is designed as general supervisor of the correct and efficient implementation of the Programme Agreement.

It is agreed that the municipality of **XXXXXXXXX** and **XXXXXXXXX** acting as a DPO, will provide, at the best of their capacities, the proper support for the implementation of the ASSERT programme.

PROCEDURES IN CASE OF FORCE MAJEURE OR SIGNIFICANT DEVIATIONS

If a situation arises that cannot be resolved at the level of day-to-day activities, and may put at risk the fulfilment of the commitments defined in this Programme Agreement, the concerned Party shall inform the Assert Project Partner (**Ecoserveis**), as early as possible. If no solution is found through direct dialogue between the Parties involved, any Party may request a dedicated meeting to jointly assess the situation.

If the situation is not resolved within a reasonable timeframe, **Ecoserveis** may propose to suspend the provision of Programme Agreement.

CONFIDENTIALITY AND DATA PROTECTION

All Parties commit to treating any information shared within the framework of this collaboration with care and respect.

i. Confidentiality

- Any non-public information shared between the Parties during the implementation of this agreement shall be considered confidential.
- Confidential information may include documents, data, personal stories, internal decisions, or any content explicitly marked as confidential.
- This information shall not be disclosed to third parties without prior written agreement from the Party who provided it, unless required by law.

ii. Personal data protection

- All Parties agree to process any personal data collected or shared in the context of this collaboration in full compliance with Article 28 of the **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR – Regulation (EU) 2016/679)** and relevant national laws.
- Personal data shall only be collected for clearly defined purposes related to the project and with appropriate legal basis (e.g. informed consent).
- The data shall be securely stored, used only for the agreed purpose, and retained only for the necessary duration.
- Special attention will be given to protecting the rights and dignity of persons with disabilities, ensuring that their data is handled in an accessible, respectful, and inclusive manner.

iii. Obligations of the Parties

- Each Party is responsible for ensuring that their staff, volunteers or subcontractors understand and comply with these rules.
- In case of any data breach or confidentiality concern, the concerned Party shall inform the other as soon as possible and cooperate in taking appropriate measures.

This commitment to confidentiality and data protection remains valid even after the end of this agreement.

DURATION AND TERMINATION

This agreement enters into force on the date of its signature by both Parties and remains valid for the duration of the Technical Assistance programme. The maximum duration of the programme is 18 months, counted from **the date of its official start**.

However, the actual timeline may be adapted according to the needs, pace and objectives of the participating entities, as long as this does not compromise the overall goals and deliverables of the ASSERT project.

Either Party may decide to terminate the agreement before its natural end, by providing written notice and a clear justification. In such cases, both Parties commit to seek a mutually acceptable solution that minimises any disruption to the beneficiaries and ensures continuity of support, where possible.

COMMUNICATION, VISIBILITY AND LANGUAGE

a. Communication tools

All communication related to the implementation of the ASSERT Programme shall be carried out via email.

Each Party agrees to designate at least one contact person and to use email as the main channel for sharing updates, materials, and coordination messages. All relevant documents and reports will be exchanged digitally, using shared folders or secure links as needed.

b. Working language of the agreement

To facilitate smooth collaboration:

Multilateral written communication among the Parties may be conducted in the **national language** of the Beneficiaries.

When possible, a **title and a short paragraph in English** should be included to help with overall project coordination.

The **Final Report** (D5.3 Report on activities of mentorship programme beneficiaries) addressed to the Beneficiaries will be **in English**. However, may also be written in the **national language**.

This approach ensures inclusivity, while also allowing the ASSERT coordination team to track and support the progress of local pilots across different countries.

SIGNATURES

For MUNICIPALITY: XXXXXXXXX

DATE: XX/XX/2025

[Name, Position]

For DPO: XXXXXXXXX

DATE: XX/XX/2025

[Name, Position]

For Consortium Partner: XXXXXXXXX

DATE: XX/XX/2025

[Name, Position]

Assert Consortium

PROJECT FACTS

Start date: 01/10/2024 **Duration:** 36M **Call:** LIFE-2023-CET **Coordinator:** AISFOR SRL (AISFOR)